

Deliverable 1.3

Data Management Plan

Version 1

WP 1
Deliverable 1.3
Lead Beneficiary: CIIMAR
Call Identifier: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03
Grant Agreement No. 101079467
Dissemination Level: DMP – Data Management Plan

Co-Funded by the European Union (GA 101079467) and the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the Research Executive Agency (REA) or the UKRI. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

Executive summary

During the project, the consortium will generate an extensive amount of data. In particular, data generated by next generation sequencing (NGS) has to be properly managed in order to be readable and usable for future research and researchers. In this way, the data treatment will be done according with FAIR principles, namely: Into each task of the scientific project several organisms will be sequenced to study and comprehend the response against virus and pathogens of the cultured fish once fed with two levels of amino-acid supplemented diets. All sequencing data will be uploaded into the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) BioProject platform (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/>) and assigned a permanent BioProject ID for identification, linked to metadata to allow full interpretation of the data. This will provide open access to the information both using web browsers and bioinformatics queries, complying with the Findable and Accessible information strategy. Also, all data generated will have an accession number that will interlink several databases such as Genebank, InterPro or PubMed. The shared vocabularies and ontologies are in concordance with the Interoperable and Reusable use of the information. All the raw data generated will be put at disposition of the scientific community as soon as generated, and then linked to open access publications.

Contents

Executive summary.....	2
Acronyms and Abbreviations.....	4
1. Introduction.....	5
2. Data summary	5
3. FAIR data.....	6
3.1. Making data findable	6
3.1.1. Data storage and archive	7
3.1.2. Sample coding	7
3.2. Making data openly accessible	9
3.2.1. Data sharing, ownership and security.....	10
3.2.2. Publication policy.....	11
3.2.3. IPR management	12
3.3. Making data interoperable	12
3.4. Making data reusable	12
4. Allocation of resources	13
5. Ethics and GDPR	14
Document Information	15

Acronyms and Abbreviations

CA	Consortium agreement
DMP	Data management plan
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability
GA	Grant Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
PCC	Project Coordination Committee
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The data management plan (DMP) describes the main elements of data management policy for the data to be collected, processed or generated in the context of the project. The DMP has been created according to the FAIR principles (data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). It is a living document and will be updated over the course of the project, with input from partners, whenever significant changes arise.

2. Data summary

The main goal of GRINNAQUA is to capacitate CIIMAR to raise staff's research profile and increase its innovation capacity positioning the institution among the main actors in the area of aquaculture. To achieve this, clear strategies are defined to raise staff's research profile and excellence, including the preparation of training workshops and summer schools (WP2), as well as research, technical and administrative training and staff exchange (WP4). The data produced in WP2 and WP4 will be mostly the result of questionnaires which will be analysed and used to determine the impact of the project actions.

The project also includes a research project focused on the high economic impact of viral and parasitic outbreaks in aquaculture, by studying the prophylactic effects of functional diets in rainbow trout against haemorrhagic septicaemia virus, and in Atlantic salmon infected sea lice (WP3). The project also outlines strategies for stakeholder engagement as a way to strengthen CIIMAR's market-driven research and innovation activities, thus increasing its competitiveness (WP5), and improved communication between science, policy, industry and society (WP6). WP1 will deal with all official administrative documentation. Table 1 further describes the WPs and tasks in the project.

Table 1: WPs and tasks in GRINNAQUA

WP	Task
1. Coordination and project management	Task 1.1: Administrative & financial management
	Task 1.2: Monitoring project implementation
	Task 1.3: Preparation & organisation of meetings
	Task 1.4: Management & Communication Portal
	Task 1.5: Project Manual

2. Specialized training for excellence	Task 2.1: Workshops
	Task 2.2: Summer Schools
	Task 2.3: Advanced training – students exchange
3. Exploratory project: Role of methionine in fish immune defences against viral and parasite infection	Task 3.1: Effects of methionine dietary supplementation on trout antiviral response
	Task 3.2: Effects of methionine supplementation on the salmon immune response against sea lice infection
4. Stimulating research and administration excellence	Task 4.1: Gaps, needs and opportunities
	Task 4.2: Short-term partnership & networking: Expert visits and staff exchange
5. Consortium sustainability	Task 5.1: Highly competitive international funding
	Task 5.2: Young researchers co-supervision
6. Communication and dissemination	Task 6.1: Communication and dissemination strategy
	Task 6.2: Communication resources and tools
	Task 6.3: Participation in events
	Task 6.4: Engagement with policy-makers
	Task 6.5: Communication with general public

Table 2. Management of research data (limited to WP3 exploratory project) in GRINNAQUA

Task	Origin of data	Form of processed raw data	Summary of results	Storage type	Dissemination level	Partners involved
3.1	Clinical evaluation data	multiple	Validation studies	computer	confidential	all
3.2	Clinical evaluation data	multiple	Validation studies	computer	confidential	all

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable

3.1.1. Data storage and archive

Following principles of good practices, the official administrative data (e.g. consortium agreement (CA), reports, deliverables, minutes, meeting presentations) are stored in the common google drive (for more information, please see D1.1 Project management and communication).

Raw data will be stored locally at each partner's facilities and according to their respective internal rules. Datasets will be processed and analysed using relevant characterization and analysis software.

3.1.2. Sample labelling

A common sample labelling system has been agreed by all partners in the project. Each experiment will be registered on a google form with all the relevant information (Figure 1). The google form will allow editing the responses so that partners can correct the information if necessary. The resulting excel file, with all common data about the experiment, will be accessible to the whole consortium but will not be editable, to avoid accidental loss of information. Codes for the samples will follow those described in tables 3 to 5.

Table 3: species code to be used in sample labelling

Species	Code
Atlantic salmon	AS
Rainbow trout	RT

Table 4: sample type code to be used in sample labelling

Sample type	Code
mucosal tissue	muc
skin	skn
plasma	pla
head-kidney	hk
blood	bld

Table 5: sample analysis code to be used in sample labelling

Sample analysis	Code
humoral	hum

transcriptome	tra
proteome	pro
cellular	cel

The sample code will always follow the same structure:

GA (to identify the GRINNAQUA project) <Task number> <species> <number of the experiment>
<sample type> < analysis>.

As an example, a first experiment in task 3.1, working with Atlantic salmon, where plasma is to be collected for humoral analysis will have the following tag: “GA 3.1 as 1 pla hum”. The sample form (Figure 1) includes information about the source of the samples but also their destination. Several sample types and analysis can be filled in for each experiment.

grinnaqua green innovation strategies for animal health management: towards sustainable aquaculture

Co-funded by the EU (GA 101079467) UK Research and Innovation

GRINNAQUA sample registration

Because GRINNAQUA is strongly collaborative, all experiments done in the context of the project should be registered and their samples should have standardized tags. Please fill in this form and use the tag according to the formula (where GA stands for GRINNAQUA):

GA|Task|Species|number of the experiment|Sample type|Analysis

(ex. Task 3.1, Atlantic Salmon, 1st experiment, Plasma, humoral)
tag: GA 3.1 AS 1 pla hum

You will receive the responses to the form on your email

Figure 1. Form for samples registration within GRINNAQUA

The resulting excel file will have the following information:

	Form questions
Filled once for each experiment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name of the researcher • E-mail • Alternative contact name (optional) • Alternative contact email (optional) • Institution • Task number • Experiment number • Title of the experiment • Date of beginning of the experiment • Species • What is being tested
As many entries as necessary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sample type • Sample analysis • Institution where samples will be sent

The acronym attributed to the experiment will link to a document with the detailed protocol, which can later be made openly available. A template for protocols within the project is available to the whole consortium in the common google drive folder, under 'GRINNAQUA – Project wide' > '3. Templates & Logos' > '4. Protocol template.docx' (Figure 2)

confidential

Trial code:			
<experiment title>			
<partner>		<partner>	
• <team member>		• <team member>	
• <team member>		<team member>	
Start date:		End date:	
Objective			
Location			
Treatments			
Diets			
Pellet size			
<species>			
Origin			
Initial weight range		Final weight range	
Initial N per tank		Tank volume	
Replicates			
Rearing conditions			
Temperature		Salinity	
Photoperiod			
Feeding		< number meals per day, manually / automatic, amount of feed and frequency of adjustments>	
Daily routines		< system maintenance and possibly feed adjustments >	

Figure 2: Template for protocols used in the GRINNAQUA project.

3.2. Making data openly accessible

3.2.1. Data sharing, ownership and security

The consortium members will use the data throughout the project. All requests for additional data uses after the project is finished will be carefully evaluated and, whenever possible, accepted by the partner(s) responsible for generating them. If there are no IPR or confidentiality concerns, or if there is no direct overlap between the study questions and the primary research, permission for data use will be granted. The partner(s) responsible for generating the data will be the rightful owner(s) of the datasets. Securing and backing up the data will be the responsibility of the partners who generated it.

All sequencing data will be uploaded into the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) BioProject platform (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/>) and assigned a permanent BioProject ID for identification, linked to metadata to allow full interpretation of the data. This will provide open access to the information both using web browsers and bioinformatics queries, complying with the Findable and Accessible information strategy. All data generated will have an accession number that will interlink several.

In order to have reproducible results for future experiments in the area of nutrition supplementation and host-parasite interactions, the GRINNAQUA consortium will provide all used scripts in open code hosting platforms such as GitHub. In this way, R or Python scripts for data analysis will be freely available to the community to increase transparency and prevent questionable research practices. In this sense, authors will release all raw results collected during the research project to allow the full scrutiny of the results and contribute to the review and improvement of the scientific process.

Workshops and webinar events will be recorded and made available on the website of the project and on YouTube (an account will be created once resources are available for publishing) and disseminated on social media. In this way, GRINNAQUA will provide advanced training in an open environment and freely available for all scientific, student and citizen community interested in the topics discussed into the project.

3.2.2. Publication policy

The GRINNAQUA project deliverables include both public and confidential documents. Project deliverables and other internal documents are frequently in the form of confidential reports, while paper publications are open to the public and will be published in peer-reviewed scientific journals. The project website, workshops, position paper and other communication materials will all serve as additional platforms for sharing project updates and knowledge gained during the project.

The dissemination and communication plan lists various channels through which the public papers and project information will be shared. Whenever feasible, the project coordinator (PC) will collaborate with the project coordination committee (PCC) to take all necessary steps to make the data freely accessible and usable for third parties for research, teaching, and study purposes through licensing or other ways.

All peer-reviewed scientific articles will be freely available. Prior notice of any planned publication and patent application shall be given to the other Parties at least 15 calendar days before the publication, as described in the GA and in D1.1 – project management and communication portal

3.2.3. IPR management

The CA contains a description of fundamental IPR ideas, which can be summarized as:

- Results are owned by the Party that generates them
- The background IP owned by the partners prior to commencement of the project is respected, and it is only non-exclusively bound to the project
- When necessary, patent applications will be submitted and approved for publication in accordance with section 3.2.2.

Exploitation and IP issues will be managed by the PC and PCC.

More information on IPR rules can be found in the GA article 16 and its annex 5 and in the CA article 8.

3.3. Making data interoperable

The standard data files will be prepared in excel or google sheets. The units used will follow the rules in table 6, as agreed by all partners

Table 6: Standard data parameters

Parameter	Unit
Length	m (metric system)
Weight	g (gram)
Temperature	°C
Language	English (UK)
Decimal characters	. (point)

3.4. Making data reusable

Most of the information produced by GRINNAQUA will be freely available under a Creative Commons license. Each dataset's metadata will provide the type of license and usage restrictions. One of the following is highly preferred:

- CC-O – Public Domain Dedication

By relinquishing all of his or her rights to the work under copyright laws everywhere, including any associated and adjacent rights, to the fullest extent permitted by law, you donated the work to the public domain.

Without seeking permission, everyone is free to copy, edit, distribute, and perform the work, even for profit.

More information on Universal Public Domain Dedication:
<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>

- CC-BY – Attribution

Anyone using your work must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

For more information on Attribution 4.0 international:
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

After the project's completion, open access data produced by GRINNAQUA will continue to be available for reuse. There are no plans to stop providing this data. As a result, it will be used once the protocols have been established or the research has been finished and published, as well as for as long as the archives last. After disclosure, access rights will rely on the creative common license that those data or goods are covered by, as stated earlier in this section. The partner using the limited datasets must arrange any necessary negotiations with the data owners for the re-use of those datasets and/or products for the products generated using restricted data.

The data provider is primarily responsible for the initial quality control of the data during data collecting. Any techniques or procedures for quality control can be described in the dataset's metadata. Datasets may need to undergo a number of quality control steps in order to be made available through the international repositories. These steps are designed to increase the accuracy and completeness of the data.

4. Allocation of resources

The PC is responsible for data management in the project. Costs related to open access publishing are included in partners' budgets.

5. Ethics and GDPR

All participants in this project are committed to responsible principles and will conform to the current legislation and regulations in countries where the research will be carried out. Ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon Europe will be rigorously applied regardless of the country in which the research is carried out. The project complies with the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU.

The general research ethics applies to the disciplines of science which are included in this proposal and will be respected. The project will observe Directive 1995/46/EC on protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and Directive 2002/58/EC on privacy and electronic communications.

When collecting personal information, for the purpose of registration in the workshops, response to the questionnaires or subscription to the newsletter, GRINNAQUA will be compliant with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), as observed by directive 2016/679.

In this project, the ethical aspects will be considered by all consortium partners and monitored by the PC. Any significant issues or deviations pertaining to the gender aspects will be reported to the PCC.

Document Information

Grant number	101079467	Acronym	GRINNAQUA
Full title	Green innovation strategies for animal health management: towards sustainable Aquaculture		
Project website	https://grinnaqua.eu		

Deliverable	Nº	1.3	Title	Data Management Plan
Work Package	Nº	1	Title	Coordination and project management
Work Package Leader	CIIMAR			
Work Participants	Tânia Pereira, Benjamin Costas, Sérgio Fernández-Boo			

Lead Beneficiary	CIIMAR
Authors	Tânia Pereira
Reviewers	Benjamin Costas, Sérgio Fernández-Boo

Due date of deliverable	30 April 2023
Submission date	
Dissemination level	Public
Type of deliverable	DMP – Data Management Plan

Version Log			
Issue Date	Revision Nº	Author	Change
17 May 2023	0.1	Tânia Pereira	First draft
18 May 2023	0.2	Sérgio Fernández-Boo	Revision
2 June 2023	1	Benjamin Costas	Submitted version